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FEATURES OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

Introduction. The EU is divided into different categories of regions, which reflect their level of development. Some regions are centers of economic activity and have a high standard of living, while other regions lag behind in development and face socio-economic problems. EU membership has influenced the development of many regions by providing access to European markets, financial resources and investment opportunities. This promotes the development of trade, infrastructure and business in EU regions.

One notable example of new regulation can be seen in Germany where the concept of "Landesplanung" was introduced, which is a comprehensive regional planning strategy. The focus is on integrated and sustainable development in various regions. This approach involves collaboration between the federal, provincial and local governments to address social, economic and environmental problems. The success of "Landesplanung" is determined by the balanced development of various regions of Germany, ensuring equal opportunities for all citizens. [1,2019.]

The regulation of regional development in Germany has a balancing act for sustainable growth. Known for its strong economy, efficient infrastructure and thriving cities, Germany owes much of its success to a well-regulated system of regional development. Germany's approach to regional development as a federal country is unique in that it strikes a delicate balance between national cohesion and local autonomy. The country's regional development structure is characterized by a dual system that divides responsibilities between the federal and state governments. The national government plays a critical role in formulating comprehensive policies and providing financial resources for regional development. It establishes the legal and regulatory framework within which states operate, ensuring consistency and harmonization across the country.

At the regional level, regional planning and development are primarily managed by state governments and their administrative bodies. These bodies work closely with local authorities, including municipalities and rural districts, to develop and implement development plans tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of each region. This decentralized approach allows for local input and accountability that ensures a coordinated and integrated national development agenda.

The principles of regional development are based on the concept of “balanced territorial development” and are aimed at achieving a harmonious distribution of economic activities, infrastructure and services across regions that reduce inequality between prosperous and disadvantaged areas.

Sustainable development is also at the heart of Germany's regional development policy, which combines economic growth with environmental protection, social cohesion and resource efficiency. Regional planning strategies include areas such as land use, renewable energy, transport networks and conservation of natural habitats. Germany, while promoting sustainable development through various mechanisms and initiatives, also strives to achieve long-term prosperity while minimizing negative impacts on the environment and society.

One of the key tools is the allocation of financial resources to the regions. The federal government provides significant funding to support infrastructure projects, innovation clusters, and regional development programs that aim to strengthen regional competitiveness, attract private investment, and stimulate job creation.

In addition, Germany encourages cooperation and knowledge sharing between regions through its networking initiatives. Platforms such as regional competitiveness networks and innovation alliances facilitate collaboration among various stakeholders, including businesses, research institutions and local governments. This exchange of experience and resources supports the development of regional specialization, promotes innovation and economic diversification.

In addition, Germany's regional development rules emphasize the importance of social cohesion. Measures are being taken to provide targeted support to disadvantaged regions, reduce regional differences and improve the living conditions of all citizens. Through initiatives such as the European Regional Development Fund, financial assistance is provided to regions facing structural challenges, allowing them to invest in education, health and social infrastructure. [4,2014]

The regulation of regional development in Germany is aimed at sustainable growth, social cohesion and fair distribution of resources. The system effectively balances national goals with local autonomy, promoting cooperation, innovation and competitiveness. By embracing the principles of balanced territorial development and sustainability, Germany continues to maintain its position as an economic power while ensuring the prosperity and well-being of its citizens throughout the country.

Moving to the Nordic region, Finland has adopted the concept of "polycentric

development" to regulate regional growth. This approach aims to decentralize economic activities by promoting the development of multiple growth centers outside the capital city. By stimulating economic activities in various regions, Finland is able to reduce regional disparities and create a more balanced and resilient economy. The success of polycentric development can be witnessed in the flourishing local economies and improved quality of life in multiple Finnish regions.

In Canada, a unique form of regional development regulation called "community-led development" has gained traction. This approach empowers local communities to take charge of their own development projects, fostering inclusivity and participatory decision-making. Through community-led development, various regions in Canada have been able to identify and prioritize their specific needs and tailor solutions accordingly. This has resulted in the successful implementation of initiatives that address the unique challenges faced by different regions, promoting sustainable development and fostering a strong sense of community ownership.

Furthermore, in Australia, the concept of "regional development alliances" has been instrumental in guiding regional growth. These alliances bring together various stakeholders, including government bodies, private organizations, and community representatives, to collaborate on regional development projects. By leveraging the diverse expertise and resources of different entities, Australia has been able to promote effective regional planning and investment, leading to improved infrastructure, job creation, and economic growth across the country.

We can see some of the exciting new forms of regulation that European countries are implementing to foster regional development.

1. Integrated Territorial Investments:

A key regulatory approach gaining traction in Europe is the concept of Integrated Territorial Investments (ITIs). ITIs encourage a holistic approach to regional development by bridging sector-based policies and geographical areas. By pooling resources from different sectors, ITIs aim to design comprehensive strategies that tackle regional disparities while leveraging strengths and opportunities unique to each territory. This form of regulation fosters cooperation across municipalities, local authorities, and regional stakeholders, enabling more effective planning, resource allocation, and implementation of development projects.

2. Smart Specialization Strategies (S3):

Many European countries have adopted Smart Specialization Strategies (S3) as a regulatory tool to enhance regional competitiveness. S3 encourages regions to

identify and concentrate on their key strengths and assets, creating a focus on specialized sectors in which they can excel. By supporting innovation, research, and entrepreneurial activities within these sectors, S3 maximizes the potential for economic growth and international competitiveness. S3 initiatives often involve close collaboration between universities, businesses, and research institutions, ensuring that the regions develop cutting-edge expertise in their chosen specializations.

3. Green Regional Development:

In recent years, Europe has witnessed a significant shift towards sustainable growth and environmental conservation. Regional development policies now focus on incorporating green principles into economic activities. Governments are implementing regulations to encourage renewable energy investments, promote circular economy practices, and support eco-tourism initiatives. These measures not only stimulate regional growth but also contribute to carbon neutrality targets, climate change mitigation, and preservation of natural resources. Green regional development regulations emphasize social and environmental sustainability, thereby fostering a more inclusive and responsible approach to economic progress.

4. Cohesion Policy and Conditionalities:

Cohesion Policy, a key European Union (EU) instrument, plays a critical role in regulating regional development across member countries. As part of the EU's multi-annual financial framework, Cohesion Policy allocates funds to regions with the aim of reducing economic disparities and enhancing overall cohesion within the Union. In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on conditionality - requiring regions to implement specific policies or reforms to access funds. By attaching conditions related to governance, sustainability, digitalization, or innovation, Cohesion Policy encourages regions to adopt best practices, increase accountability, and ensure effective utilization of investments.

European countries are continuously reevaluating their regulatory frameworks to ensure efficient and sustainable regional development. By adopting these innovative regulatory strategies, European countries are equipping their regions with the tools and resources necessary for long-term growth, competitiveness, and social inclusion. As Europe adapts to new challenges, the dynamism and adaptability of its regulatory framework will play a crucial role in shaping its regional development landscape.

In conclusion, foreign countries in particular have embraced various innovative forms of regulation to promote sustainable and balanced regional development. Whether it's the comprehensive regional planning strategy in

Germany, the polycentric development approach in Finland, community-led development in Canada, or regional development alliances in Australia, these initiatives have proven their efficacy in addressing the unique challenges faced by different regions. By adopting and adapting these successful practices, countries around the world can ensure the overall development and prosperity of their regions, paving the way for a brighter future.

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